

Supplementary Materials

Table 3.1

S1: Demographic Information Profile (N=1527)

Respondent's Characteristics		<i>f (%)</i>	<i>M(SD)</i>	
Age			24.89(2.21)	
Gender	Male	795 (52.20)		
	Female	732 (47.80)		
Education	Master	1383 (90.60)		
	PhD	144 (9.40)		
University	University of Punjab	151 (9.90)		
	Lahore College for Women University	137 (9.00)		
	Government College University Faisalabad	155 (10.20)		
	Arid Agriculture University	171 (11.20)		
	University of Gujrat	166 (10.90)		
	University of Sahiwal	171 (11.20)		
	Islamia University of Bahawalpur	161 (10.50)		
	Bahauddin Zakariya University	138 (9.00)		
	University of Sargodha	150 (9.80)		
	Ghazi University	127 (8.30)		
	Faculty	Faculty of Science	507 (33.20)	
		Faculty of Arts and Humanities	513 (33.60)	
Faculty of Social Sciences		507 (33.20)		
Mathematics		170 (11.10)		
Physics		178 (11.70)		
Chemistry		158 (10.30)		
English		161 (10.50)		
Departments	Urdu	180 (11.80)		
	Islamic Studies	173 (11.30)		
	Psychology	170 (11.10)		
	Economics	171 (11.20)		
	Sociology	166 (10.90)		
Family Monthly Income (in Pakistani Rupees)			70355.60 (40838.43)	
Home Residence	Urban	615 (40.30)		
	Rural	912 (59.70)		
Marital Status	Unmarried	1251 (81.90)		
	Married	268 (17.60)		
	Divorced	08 (0.50)		
Family System	Separate	782 (51.20)		
	Joint	745 (48.80)		

1	I have so much in life to be thankful for.							
2	If I had to list everything that I felt grateful for, it would be a very long list.							
3	When I look at the world, I don't see much to be grateful for.							
4	I am grateful to a wide variety of people.							
5	As I get older I find myself more able to appreciate the people, events, and situations that have been part of my life history.							
6	Long amounts of time can go by before I feel grateful to something or someone.							

S4b: Heartland Forgiveness Scale

Directions:

In the course of our lives negative things may occur because of our own actions, the actions of others, or circumstances beyond our control. For some time after these events, we may have negative thoughts or feelings about ourselves, others, or the situation. Think about how you typically respond to such negative events. Next to each of the following items write the number (from the 7-point scale below) that best describes how you typically respond to the type of negative situation described. There are no right or wrong answers. Please be as open as possible in your answers.

Sr. No	Statement	Almost Always False of Me	Almost False of Me	More Often False of Me	Neutral	More Often True of Me	Almost True of Me	Almost Always True of Me
1	Although I feel badly at first when I mess up, over time I can give myself some slack.							
2	I hold grudges against myself for negative things I've done.							
3	Learning from bad things that I've done helps me get over them.							
4	It is really hard for me to accept myself once I've messed up.							
5	With time I am understanding of myself for mistakes I've made.							
6	I don't stop criticizing myself for negative things I've felt, thought, said, or done.							
7	I continue to punish a person who has done something that I think is wrong.							
8	With time I am understanding of others for the mistakes they've made.							

9	I continue to be hard on others who have hurt me.								
10	Although others have hurt me in the past, I have eventually been able to see them as good people.								
11	If others mistreat me, I continue to think badly of them.								
12	When someone disappoints me, I can eventually move past it.								
13	When things go wrong for reasons that can't be controlled, I get stuck in negative thoughts about it.								
14	With time I can be understanding of bad circumstances in my life.								
15	If I am disappointed by uncontrollable circumstances in my life, I continue to think negatively about them.								
16	I eventually make peace with bad situations in my life.								
17	It's really hard for me to accept negative situations that aren't anybody's fault.								

18	Eventually I let go of negative thoughts about bad circumstances that are beyond anyone's control							
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S4c: Spirituality Scale

Please indicate your level of agreement to the following statements by circling the appropriate number that corresponds with the answer key.

Sr. No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Mostly disagree	Mostly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I find meaning in my life experiences.						
2	I have a sense of purpose.						
3	I am happy about the person I have become.						
4	I see the sacredness in everyday life.						
5	I meditate to gain access to my inner spirit						
6	I live in harmony with nature.						
7	I believe there is a connection between all things that I cannot see but can sense.						
8	My life is a process of becoming.						
9	I believe in a Higher Power/Universal Intelligence.						
10	I believe that all living creatures deserve respect.						

11	The earth is sacred.						
12	I value maintaining and nurturing my relationships with others.						
13	I use silence to get in touch with myself.						
14	I believe that nature should be respected.						
15	I have a relationship with a Higher Power/Universal Intelligence.						
16	My spirituality gives me inner strength.						
17	I am able to receive love from others.						
18	My faith in a Higher Power/Universal Intelligence helps me cope during challenges in my life.						
19	I strive to correct the excesses in my own lifestyle patterns/practices.						
20	I respect the diversity of people.						
21	Prayer is an integral part of my spiritual nature.						
22	At times, I feel at one with the universe.						
23	I often take time to assess my life choices as a way of living my spirituality						

S4d: Meaning in Life Questionnaire

Please take a moment to think about what makes your life feel important to you. Please respond to the following statements as truthfully and accurately as you can, and also please remember that these are very subjective questions and that there are no right or wrong answers. Please answer according to the scale below:

Sr. No	Statement	Absolutely Untrue	Mostly Untrue	Somewhat Untrue	Can't Say True or False	Somewhat True	Mostly True	Absolutely True
1	I understand my life's meaning.							
2	I am looking for something that makes my life feel meaningful.							
3	I am always looking to find my life's purpose.							
4	My life has a clear sense of purpose.							
5	I have a good sense of what makes my life meaningful.							
6	I have discovered a satisfying life purpose.							
7	I am always searching for something that makes my life feel significant.							

8	I am seeking a purpose or mission for my life.							
9	My life has no clear purpose.							
10	I am searching for meaning in my life.							

S4e: Mental Health Inventory

Please indicate your level of agreement to the following statements by circling the appropriate number that corresponds with the answer key.

Sr. No	Statement	Always	Very often	Fairly often	Sometimes	Almost never	Never
1	How happy, satisfied, or pleased have you been with your personal life during the past month?						
2	How much of the time have you felt lonely during the past month?						
3	How often did you become nervous or jumpy when faced with excitement or unexpected situations during the past month?						
4	During the past month, how much of the time have you felt that the future looks hopeful and promising?						
5	How much time, during the past month, has your daily life been full of things that were interesting to you?						

6	How much time, during the past month, did you feel relaxed and free from tension?						
7	During the past month, how much of the time have you generally enjoyed the things you do?						
8	During the past month, have you had any reason to wonder if you were losing your mind, or losing control over the way you act, talk, think, feel or of your memory?						
9	Did you feel depressed during the past month?						
10	During the past month, how much of the time have you felt loved and wanted?						
11	How much time, during the past month, have you been a very nervous person?						
12	When have you got up in the morning, this past month, about how often did you expect to have an interesting day?						
13	During the past month, how much of the time have you felt tense or "high strung"?						
14	During the past month, have you been in firm control of your behavior, thoughts, emotions or feelings?						

15	During the past month, how often did your hands shake when you tried to do something?						
16	During the past month, how often did you feel that you had nothing to look forward to?						
17	How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt calm and peaceful?						
18	How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt emotionally stable?						
19	How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt downhearted and blue?						
20	How often have you felt like crying, during the past month?						
21	During the past month, how often have you felt that others would be better off if you were dead?						
22	How much of the time, during the past month, were you able to relax without difficulty?						
23	How much of the time, during the past month, did you feel that your love relationships, loving and being loved, were full and complete?						
24	How often, during the past month, did you feel that						

	nothing turned out for you the way you wanted it to?						
25	How much have you been bothered by nervousness, or your "nerves", during the past month?						
26	During the past month, how much of the time has living been a wonderful adventure for you?						
27	How often, during the past month, have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?						
28	During the past month, did you think about taking your own life?						
29	During the past month, how much of the time have you felt restless, fidgety, or impatient?						
30	During the past month, how much of the time have you been moody or brooded about things?						
31	How much of the time, during the past month, have you felt cheerful, lighthearted?						
32	During the past month, how often did you get rattled, upset or flustered?						
33	During the past month, have you been anxious or worried?						

34	During the past month, how much of the time were you a happy person?						
35	How often, during the past month, did you find yourself trying to calm down?						
36	During the past month, how much of the time have you been in low or very low spirits?						
37	How often, during the past month, have you been waking up feeling fresh and rested?						
38	During the past month, have you been under or felt you were under any strain, stress or pressure?						